

Soft Skills for Hard Impact

A roadmap for including Open Science in post-graduate training curricula

**FOSTER & FOSTER+ Product
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Glossary of terms:

DOI	digital object identifier
EC	European Commission
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
OS	Open Science
RDM	Research Data Management
REF	Research Excellence Framework, UK
ROI	return on investment
TDM	Text/Data Mining
RRI	Responsible Research & Innovation

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Figure 1. Ecosystem of Key Actors in research process that govern long-term Open Science integration in the knowledge generation process. Each group is a potential barrier or enabler along the young researcher’s career path. Societal Impact through Citizen Science, Public Engagement and Co-creation are all emerging external forces that will also influence Open Science uptake, and are likely to be criteria in future research evaluation criteria. 7

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Targeting early-career-stage researchers (PhDs and postdocs) is essential in enabling a cultural shift.

Science Europe & Global Research Council Surveys, Oct 2016

“
It is important that the way the REF is designed continues to ... act as a positive contribution to the sharing of research through its requirements over open access and open data.

Lord Stern review of REF, UK Jan-July 2016

“
Collaborations – an open, friendly environment where people work together to achieve things faster rather than competing needlessly.

Survey respondent, “The Culture of Scientific Research.” 2014, Nuffield Council on Bioethics, December 2014

“
change assessment, evaluation and reward systems in science to account for the impact of scientific research on society, and incentivise citizen science

Amsterdam Call for Action on “Open Science: From Vision to Action”, hosted by the Netherlands’ EU Presidency on 4 Apr 2016

“
we are in a new era of global & Open Science : a return to founding principles of science

[EC Commissioner for Research & Innovation, Carlos Moedas, July 2016](#)
[Speech at ESOF 2016 Manchester](#)

“
Open access can certainly fit in with institutional agendas including in particular impact (academic and societal) agendas.

Declaration on Research Assessment, December 2012

“
replace research impact indicators beyond the typical bibliometrics and patenting

Horizon2020 Societal Challenge 6 Research Priority for “Better integration of evidence on the impact of research and innovation in policy making” 2016-2017

Rationale:

Open Science (OS) offers researchers tools and workflows for transparency, reproducibility, dissemination and transfer of new knowledge.

Ultimately, this can also have an impact on in research evaluation exercises, e.g. Research Excellence Framework (REF), set to demand greater “*societal impact*” in future, rather than just research output^{1, 2}.

The Open Science policy priority by the European Commission has expanded beyond just Open Access to the peer-reviewed research publications, but also open data, research software, educational resources, policy briefs.

This arguably requires a more coordinated and strategic institutional approach to documenting, disseminating and promoting the uptake of research output for the benefit of society and speeding up towards solutions of today’s Societal Challenges. Impact (16) is a central issue but new ways of defining and measuring impact becoming more important many of these driven by greater openness³.

This brief presents the discrepancy between today’s measures of success for research focused on Impact Factor, and expected near future research evaluation metrics focused on broader research outputs. The approach presented argues that Graduate Schools are a key actor in the uptake of Open Science practices for reproducible and re-usable research, and that training today’s graduates in Open Science prepares them best for new research evaluation criteria likely to be developed and implemented by the time they are in their mid-career.

“

*The outputs from scientific research are many and varied, including: research articles reporting new knowledge, data, reagents, and software; intellectual property; and **highly trained young scientists***

”

Declaration on Research Assessment, Dec 2012

¹ Weighting of research impact confirmed for 2014 Research Excellence Framework <http://www.hefce.ac.uk/news/newsarchive/2011/news62310.html>, 2011

² Research Excellence Framework Review - Publications - GOV.UK., July 2016 <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/research-excellence-framework-review>

³ Pinfield, 2015. “Making Open Access Work: The ‘state-of-the-Art’ in Providing Open Access to Scholarly Literature.” *Online Information Review* 39, no. 5: 604–36. doi:10.1108/OIR-05-2015-0167

Objectives for this ROADMAP

The disparity between how the future generation of researchers is trained in a prevalent “publish or perish” environment over-relying on the Impact Factor, and how they are likely to be evaluated for tenure and institutional research evaluations with focus on broader research output, potentially places current graduates at a disadvantage to perform to such measures.

The **overarching objective** of this document is to propose simple first steps for Graduate Schools to pro-actively include Open Science training in existing “**soft skills**” classes and summer schools, in order to prepare graduates for publishing, disseminating and promoting the full diversity of research output in order to better prepare for future research evaluation criteria.

Rather than treating Open Science as a stand-alone skillset that merits its own training course, the approach aims at integrating the skillset in existing curricula following advice by Graduate Schools.

The approach also aims to rely as much as possible on support from other key professionals that influence a young scientist career path (Figure 1), so that Open Science is trained in the context of daily challenges (dissemination of research output, visibility and impact, building up a CV for tenure, or skills for alternative careers, fundraising for one’s research ideas, contribution to institutional research evaluations).

Figure 1. Ecosystem of Key Actors in research process that govern long-term Open Science integration in the knowledge generation process. Each group is a potential barrier or enabler along the young researcher’s career path. Societal Impact through Citizen Science, Public Engagement and Co-creation are all emerging external forces that will also influence Open Science uptake, and are likely to be criteria in future research evaluation criteria (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.49960).

Calibrating the Vocabulary: What do we mean by “Open Science”?

Openness to research output from **any** discipline is now a policy priority of the EC (as well as many private funders). While the correct term has been under debate (open research, open scholarship, versus open science), we use the term “open science” as the term accepted in policy jargon and formulation as the imperfect, but functional term that allow a dialogue between academia and policy makers.

While the term may be imperfect, the underlying approach of both the FOSTER Community and the mission of this roadmap, is to be **discipline agnostic**, cover all research that generates new knowledge, and apply tools and principles to making **any and all new knowledge** more accessible and reusable.

The “**science**” part of “open science” as use throughout this document, **does not in any way refer to one set of disciplines** and exclude another.

Engaging ERA’s Graduate Schools: the consultation process

The content summarizes outcome of FOSTER Project engagement efforts with Graduate Schools in the European Research Area (ERA) between 2014-2016.

FOSTER consulted Graduate School administrators through several consultations and ad-hoc events:

Engaging Finald’s Doctoral Schools, 20 Oct 2014

Open Science: Engaging Finland's Doctoral Schools

20 October 2014

Ministry of Education and Culture, Ivo Grigorov (FOSTER)
Biomedicum Helsinki Haartmaninkatu 8

FOSTER-UNESCO Open Science for Doctoral Schools, 24-25 Apr 2015

FOSTER-UNESCO Open Science for Doctoral Schools

23-24 April 2015

Bhanu Neupane (UNESCO), Joy Davidson (DCC), Nancy Pontika (OU) Ivo Grigorov (FOSTER)
1 rue Miollis, 75015 Paris, France

and events of opportunity:

MSCA Event Future of the Doctorate, 28-29 May 2015,

Future of the Doctorate

28 May 2015

EC MSCA Office

EGU2015 Session “Supporting Master and Ph.D. students: Concepts of graduate and postgraduate education” attendees of “Soft Skills for Hard Impact” Workshop, 12 Apr 2015

as well as other various training events in the [FOSTER 2015-2016 Training Calendar](#).

The participants in the various consultations and discussions were self-selecting participants and may not be representative of the wider Doctoral Schools community. Full list of attendees are on the events webpages.

What does the Community ask for?

A 2014 survey⁴ of US-based postdoctoral students on the current state of science demonstrates that the young researchers community is very aware of the challenges and potential means to improve the current state of research, and research training (Figure 2).

Postgraduates understand the failings of the current metrics and professional reward system to incentivise the right research practices that support the top-down, funders agendas on Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) and Code of Conduct.

Figure 2. Do postgraduate appreciate how Open Science contributes to better science? McDowell et al., 2015

Postgraduates are also very appreciative of the complementarity of Open Science practices to better ways of performing rigorous and reproducible research, better science communication, as well as re-use of their research outputs. The community also explicitly

⁴ McDowell et al., 2015. Shaping the Future of Research: A Perspective from Junior Scientists, F1000Research, January 9, 2015. doi:[10.12688/f1000research.5878.2](https://doi.org/10.12688/f1000research.5878.2).

requests **better training on RRI skills** (of which Open Science is one) and **a suitable incentives system** that support such practices by default in the research process.

The postgraduate community echoes research performing organizations concerns about the lack of proper incentives that motivate researcher's behavior more focused on societal impact of research (cf signatories of the [DORA Declaration](#) since 2012⁵).

The need to rehaul the research evaluation systems away from the “traditional bibliometrics and patents” and towards incentivising and rewarding a broad range of research activities and outputs, has also been echoed in the UK in 2014⁶ and more recently by the [Amsterdam Call to Action on Open Science](#) hosted by The Netherlands 2016 EC Presidency.

The trend points to research funders (both public and private) formulating mandates⁷ on making Open Science part of the standard conditions for funding.

Some Member States like Finland⁸ are also formulating ambitious Open Science targets for 2020 in order to bring research output within reach of the knowledge-based economy, and accelerate development of new services, products and solutions to Societal Challenges.

What do Graduate Schools seek?

Graduate Schools agreed that Open Science practices can have impact postgraduates visibility of research output, optimize knowledge mapping especially in cross-disciplinary research, and reduce duplication.

However, professionals designing the post-graduate curriculum find themselves in a transition period where the schools measures of success and the current incentives system do not enable uptake of Open Science in the standard research process.

The top 3 measures of success reported by schools are:

1. Number of Post-graduates students recruited consistently;
2. Number of high-quality publications per post-graduate;
3. Skills that lead to many career options.

While Open Science cannot address recruitment of postgraduates into science directly, it can contribute meaningfully (and arguable in a measurable way) to publications visibility and skills downstream of research itself that could lead to alternative career options.

⁵ San Francisco Declaration on Research Assessment (DORA) <http://www.ascb.org/dora/>

⁶ Nuffield Council on Bioethics. “The Culture of Scientific Research.” Nuffield Bioethics, December 2014. <http://nuffieldbioethics.org/project/research-culture/>

⁷ Registry of Open Access Repository Mandates and Policies <https://roarmap.eprints.org/>

⁸ “Open Science and Research Leads to Surprising Discoveries and Creative Insights Open Science and Research Roadmap 2014–2017 Reports of the Ministry of Education and Culture, Finland 2014:21.” Accessed April 7, 2015. <http://www.minedu.fi/export/sites/default/OPM/Julkaisut/2014/liitteet/okm21.pdf?lang=fi>.

What do Schools offer?

Graduate Schools that took part in the various consultations tend to offer the minimal “Open Access” training as part of “information literacy” and very few pointed to structured “Data Management”, “Research Software publishing” or other Open Science courses.

Statistics + Numerical Skills	Scientific Courses	Career Orientation	Communication	Personal Skills	Gender
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Introduction to R ● Biostatistics ● Multivariate Analysis ● MA TLAB Intro ● MA TLAB advanced ● MA TLAB / Octave ● Numerical Modelling ● Data Mining ● Scientific Programming 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Acoustic Imaging ● Microscopy ● Data Management ● Ocean Data View ● Python Programming ● ImageJ ● GIS Intro ● GIS I + II ● Mass Spec. & Optical Spectroscopy ● Microscopic Imaging ● Leibniz-Lab Intro ● Good Scientific Practice ● Carbon Footprint ● Ocean Data Bases ● "Big Questions" Lectures ● Marine Conservation ● Law of the Sea 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Getting started with the doctorate ● Stepping Stones ● Project Management ● Peer Reviewing ● Innovation ● Application Training ● Life after a PhD ● Career Planning ● University Teaching ● Hochschuldidaktik ● Grant Writing ● Selbständig machen 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Writing Lab ● Presentation Techn. ● Getting Research Publ. ● Make a good paper excellent ● Postergestaltung ● Pop.wiss. Schreiben ● Academic Writing ● Scientific Graphs ● Open Access Publishing ● Moderationstraining ● Questions, please 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Peer Coaching ● Student or Player ● Photoshop ● Flash-Animation ● Intercultural Competence 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Das Ruder in die Hand nehmen ● Realitäts-Check: "Can I have it all?"*

Figure 3. Integrating Open Science in existing Soft Skills training: an example from IOOS-Future Ocean Cluster, Kiel, Germany

Independent of the Graduate Schools consultation process, a preliminary attempt to identify current trends in Open Science training initiatives for graduate students across Europe selected a number of universities from different countries on the basis of the Scimago Ranking Web of Universities, Europe (<http://www.webometrics.info/en/Europe>). Scimago currently lists more than 6,000 institutions. Among the various academic rankings available worldwide, this ranking takes into account the institutional **web presence of a repository and open access scholarly materials, as indicators of the transfer of scientific and cultural knowledge generated by the universities to society.**

The partial analysis of these 6,000 institutions, cross sampled: 1) universities ranked from 1 to 20; b) 500 to 510; c) 1000-1010. A sample of 40 institutions websites were visited from 18 countries: UK, Germany, Italy, Norway, Belgium, France, Netherlands, Portugal, Spain, Switzerland, Czech Republic, Denmark, Finland, Iceland, Lithuania, Macedonia, Romania and Turkey.

For each institution, the website of doctoral studies and doctoral schools, if any, were examined in order to analyse their doctoral training programmes and courses, seminars,

workshops or any other events related to Open Science topics as structured in [FOSTER Open Science Taxonomy](#)⁹ and [FOSTER Open Science Learning Objectives](#).

A set of high level topics were selected, namely:

Open Access, Open Data, Data Management,

Open Science Tools, Repositories & Ethics.

Also, more general topics were taken into account as potential placements for Open Science content, as research methods, research ethics, publishing and disseminating research, outreach to society and social media for researchers.

The preliminary analysis of the 40 schools subsample indicate a clear difference between high and low ranked institutions with respect to Open Science training (NB: low ranked institutions are also smaller, local and not as research oriented).

“
none propose a general course
devoted explicitly to (Open Science)
”
LIBER Preliminary Assessment

Larger Doctorate schools that coordinate the diverse training offer, especially on transferable skills, tend to have **a higher number of courses offered on topics related to Open Science**, but **none of them propose a general course** devoted explicitly to this skillset.

Highly ranked institutions (predominantly from the UK) offer training related to Open Access and Research Data Management, while those with a lower rank are usually limited to research methods, writing and publishing, approaching

Open Access very tangentially. **Cause and effect was not analysed and is not implied.**

Highly ranked institutions tend to offer coordinated training programs with different services within the institutions, where libraries usually provide some training modules or resources on open access, research data management, and publishing strategies.

A more comprehensive study is needed, as well as further analysis of the data gathered in order to confirm the trends quantitatively.

Barriers & Opportunities for more Open Science in the Curriculum

⁹ Pontika, N., Knoth, P., Cancellieri, M., & Pearce, S., (2015). Fostering Open Science to Research using a Taxonomy and an eLearning Portal. In: iKnow: 15th International Conference on Knowledge Technologies and Data Driven Business, 21 - 22 October 2015, Graz, Austria. <http://doi.org/10.1145/2809563.2809571>

Attendees and participants in ad hoc consultations tend to agree with surveys that point to graduate demand for a more Open Research system, aligned with career path and incentives, but feel the challenge is too great to handle at a local institutional level.

In order to facilitate Open Science inclusion in curricula, Graduate Schools Administrators placed priority on:

- Open Science **training must be linked to career path(s)**;
- Open Science should **compliment existing Science Communication** Training;
- **Modular courses** (OA, OD, OSoftware) that can fit different curricula structures but also **allow self-learning**, and allow Schools to **use existing/own certification/validation** methodologies;

Consistent **concerns about Implement Open Science in the Curriculum** that persisted through the 2014-2016 period, include:

- **Uncertainty of institutional capacity** (Knowledge Managers & researchers teaching graduates) to deal with Openness of the entire Research Lifecycle, especially **in data-intensive disciplines**;
- Efficient Open Data **protocols that do not distract students** from the research process;
- **Discipline-specific Research Data Management practices** and long-term archiving alternative infrastructure, where local (and/or institutional) repositories are not available;
- **Data mining, data handling and data transformation capacity in data intensive disciplines**, leading to enhanced and more sophisticated support for large data mining and large data manipulation training for graduates;
- **Software archiving**, versioning and publishing in peer-reviewed journals;
- Optimising **career profile visibility and impact based on Open Science** (e.g. capitalising on research output publishing in a way that is aligned with expected emerging research evaluation criteria focused on “societal impact” of research).

Is there a lack of institutional capacity: Surfing the Science Cloud wave

The task will focus on FP7 RECODE Recommendations¹⁰ “formal training 4 librarians needed to transition to OpenScience”, “librarians must provide rsrch data services for

¹⁰ RECODE Recommendation for Open Access to Research Data <http://policy.recodeproject.eu/assets/recode-handbook.pdf>

Digital Age”, and building capacity for “data centers to enhance rsrch librarians data skills, RDM & data services”. The data science skillset of librarians and knowledge managers is also a demand by Graduate Schools consulted during the FOSTER Project (2014-2016) alined with EU Open Science Cloud needs on boosting skills on “new skills in data science, data analysis and visualisation”¹¹ and “text and data mining of content”¹². The training will be structured and address [FP7 FOSTER Learning Objectives for Librarians](#)¹³, build on the 2015 pilot¹⁴ and will aim to develop a program that allows optimum online participation for free, and create a DST4L Constitution that communicates the ethos of the training concept to build capacity among research librarians to support Open Science integration in the research process, and maximise multiplication of the training philosophy regionally and between LIBER Annual Meetings, and beyond LIBER Membership.

Is there a GAP? How are Graduates likely to be evaluated in their mid-career?

There is a hiathus between what Graduate Schools (and institutions) define as a measure of success, and the current community climate on how research should be evaluated in the next 5-10 yrs timeframe.

In 2012, the Declaration of Research Assessment released recommendations since signed by 822 research organisations and learned societies:

“consider the value and impact of all research outputs (including datasets and software) in addition to research publications, and consider a broad range of impact measures including qualitative indicators of research impact, such as influence on policy and practice”¹⁵.

This echoes the young researchers public demands and recommendations (MacDowell et al 2015) and was further reinforced in 2016 Amsterdam Call for Action on Open Science during the Dutch Presidency of the EU.

This expected rate of change of the evaluation system, and the variable definitions of measure of success places graduates trained in schools today, at a potential disadvantage for measuring up to the broader suit of evaluation indicators “*beyond the typical bibliometrics & patenting*”.

¹¹ Shaping the Open Science Cloud of the Future, 2015 EGI Community Forum Organised by EGI, EUDAT, GEANT and OpenAIRE.,” November 18, 2015. <http://go.egi.eu/oscws15>

¹² Amsterdam Call for Action on Open Science, Recommendations on “Facilitating Text and Data Mining of Content” 2016 <https://english.eu2016.nl/documents/reports/2016/04/04/amsterdam-call-for-action-on-open-science>

¹³ FOSTER Open Science Learning Objectives, 2015 <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15603>

¹⁴ DST4L2015 <http://www.altbibl.io/dtu/speakers/>

¹⁵ Declaration on Research Assessment (Dora) 2012. <http://www.ascb.org/dora/>

The 2016 [Research Evaluation Framework review by Lord Stern](#)¹⁶, and proposed measures for 2021 in the UK, suggests that all researchers will have to submit 2 publications of their choice. This offers the opportunity to counter the “Publish or Perish” culture with publish fewer, but explain, translate, promote, re-use, engage more.

The EC is now answering the sustained community calls to a culture change with a portfolio of call exceeding 120 Million EUR across Societal Challenge 6 Inclusive Societies, and Science with and for Society.

Research priorities are focused on developing new alternative quantitative models for assessing the societal impact of a broad range of research outputs. Final results of these calls are likely to be released by 2019-2020.

A significant part of the research portfolio is also focused on a significant culture change within academia, and stimulating institutions to integrate principles and practices of Responsible Research & Innovation (RRI has 6 pillars of which Open Science is one).

The suite of culture change calls will fund projects in the 2017-2020 period, placing incentives and designing high profile case studies for adopting the new broad measures for assessing the societal impact of research, and “[Putting Open Science into Action](#)”.

Soft Skills for Hard Impact: Can Open Science help?

The essential complement of skills beyond research excellence and rigor of method, are usually referred to as “**soft skills**”.

¹⁶ Research Excellence Framework (REF) review: Building on success and learning from experience , UK Government Publication July 2016 https://www.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/541338/ind-16-9-ref-stern-review.pdf

This can include a wide variety of skills that can directly respond to Graduate Schools criteria for success, like multiplying impact of peer-reviewed publications and skills for alternative careers (cf [VITAE Researcher Development Framework](#)¹⁷).

Such “soft skills” can produce measurable and concrete impact for career development, both in as well as beyond academia, but are not provided systematically by graduate schools alongside research excellence training.

Whether graduates aim to make a career in research, or use the skills learned in alternative careers, Graduate Schools aim at publishing postgraduates research as high-quality output.

Recently, the question of reproducibility and conduct has been high on the agenda with conflicting studies on the gravity of the situation^{18,19}.

Figure 4. Is there a reproducibility crisis? Nature doi:10.1038/533452a

While the goal for Open Science is not to « police » reproducibility, it does offer meaningful approaches to improve the perception of the current situation (Figure 4).

If the focus of future research evaluation metric is to converge on research outputs, rather than just the high-impact journal peer-reviewed publication, then Open Science can provide a collection of best practices, tools and methods to transform the average discipline’s research lifecycle from one focused on Impact Factor, to one that **underpins reproducibility** and reduces the ubiquity of human errors through optimal access for independent validation of method and outputs (Figure 5).

¹⁷ VITAE Researcher Development Framework <https://www.vitae.ac.uk/researchers-professional-development/about-the-vitae-researcher-development-framework/developing-the-vitae-researcher-development-framework>

¹⁸ Over half of psychology studies fail reproducibility test, Nature doi:10.1038/nature.2015.18248

¹⁹ Psychology’s reproducibility problem is exaggerated – say psychologists, Nature doi:10.1038/nature.2016.19498

Figure 5. Research Lifecycle transparency and impact augmented by Open Science tools & practices, and documented in an ORCID author profile to match emerging funder priorities.

Each step of the Research Lifecycle can now benefit to various degrees, by tools, approaches and best practices that contribute to transparency, optimal independent validation, access to research output by unforeseen stakeholders, citizen scientists and garage innovators, and ultimately optimal re-use.

The return on investment for the individual researcher (postgraduate) is multiplication of the publishing avenues for the immediate term while “Publish or Perish” culture changes to one more geared towards societal impact and engagement. In the mid- to long-term, graduates prepare to deal with emerging issues of **engaging society** in the research process, “**co-creation**”²⁰ and **Open Innovation**, all of which can impact their grant proposal success rate, as well their individual evaluations in future.

Building Blocks for Open Science training in the Curriculum

Assuming the institutions see the mid-term benefits for their graduates, and are ready to re-arrange already over-burdened postgraduate curricula with locally relevant modules in Open

²⁰ Definition of co-creation, based on which the concept is applied to EC Horizon 2020 research and innovation actions <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Co-creation>

Science, Global Education Leaders Partnership²¹ proposes three essential elements, based on international analysis and trials for radical changes in educational systems:

- **Build a case for Change**, to attract institutional support (resources : success stories from OpenAIRE and FOSTER Communities that match emerging research assessment criteria towards measurable societal impact of research output)
- **Develop New Pedagogies** (resources : a Taxonomy of terms for Open Science²² that maps Open Science on the average Research Lifecycle of your disciplien, and [FOSTER Open Science Learning Objectives](#)²³ to structure training in a modular way that best compliments existng curricula (e.g. Figure 3), fits local institutional needs, and capitalises on existing institutional capacities)
- **Resources to Compliment existing curricula** (resources : [FOSTER moderated or self-learning e-course modules](#) and [Portal content](#) ; [OpenAIRE Webinar Training](#), FP7 [RRI-Tools Portal & Resources](#)) HEIRRI Project, ENRRICH Project and communities dealing with Code of Conduct.

Strategies for Open Science in the Curriculum

The following a suggested and non-exhaustive strategies for boosting post-graduate capacity to use Open Science to personal career, and institutional advantages. The proposed new skillsets attempt to span the average Research Lifecycle, and cover the majority of research outputs and research effort in order to match the expected broader Research Evaluation metrics “**beyond the traditional bibliometrics and patents**”.

The strategies are presented in a 1-5 scale with increasing level of commitment by the institution, training and building capacity to support Open Science practices. The proposed approach attempts to integrate Open Science in the cloud of other so called “**soft skills**” that make are critical part of Responsible Research & Innovation (RRI), nut also support Graduate Schools current measures of success, as well as preparing graduate for a future evaluation metrics that will take account of all outputs arising from research.

Level 1: The Basics

²¹ Global Education Leaders Partnership <http://gelponline.org/>

²² Pontika, et al., 2015. Fostering Open Science to Research using a Taxonomy and an eLearning Portal. In: iKnow: 15th International Conference on Knowledge Technologies and Data Driven Business, 21 - 22 October 2015 , Graz, Austria <http://doi.org/10.1145/2809563.2809571>

²³ FOSTER Open Science Learning Objectives, 2015. Zenodo. 10.5281/zenodo.15603

Explain and meet the basic requirements of funders` Open Access and Open Data mandates, as part of existing research methodology or “information literacy” training.

Rationale: your graduates are exposed to the minimal research practice expected in order to fund their academic career.

Seek local support from: your librarians; Project Managers; Funding/Contracts Offices; experienced researchers regularly applying for research funds, EC Guidelines on Mandates requirements.

Level 2: Collaborative Workflow

Provide training on e-science and collaborative online platforms that enable efficient collaboration within local research teams, and also document the research process and diverse outputs following minimal best practice for archiving, documenting and access by new collaborators.

Rationale: your graduates are capable to use a version of electronic Lab Notebooks, keeping accessible and structured record of the research trial-and-error reiteration, curating all output for publication in diverse forms, at a chosen moment.

Seek local support from: your librarians; [Open Science Framework](#); [MyScienceWorks](#).

Level 3: Diverse Research Output

In addition to the above, pro-actively train data science, data discovery, Research Data Management (RDM) incorporating FAIR Data Principles²⁴ (possibly the research value of publishing negative results²⁵) in existing “research methodology” and “how to publish research” classes.

While data science skills facilitate mapping and navigating through the vast research data landscape, RDM and FAIR Principles best practices ensure that data is generated and curated in a way that allows transdisciplinary exploitation beyond its original purpose for generation. FAIR best practices are also presented as essential for rigorous and reproducible research open to independent validation, and fully supported by institutional e-infrastructure and RDM expertise.

Graduates are introduced to relevant options for peer-reviewed data product publications, as incentive for adhering to RDM and FAIR practices.

For relevant disciplines, structured training on Research Software code best practices, metadata, long-term archiving, including options for peer-reviewed publication of code.

²⁴ Wilkinson, M., et al. 2016. The FAIR Guiding Principles for Scientific Data Management and Stewardship. Scientific Data 3 (March 15, 2016): 160018. doi:[10.1038/sdata.2016.18](https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.18)

²⁵ Granqvist, E., 2015 Why Science Needs to Publish Negative Results, March 2015. <https://www.elsevier.com/authors-update/story/innovation-in-publishing/why-science-needs-to-publish-negative-results>

Rationale: your graduates can provide transparency and traceability for many across their Research Workflow, exploiting multiple peer-reviewed journal publication avenues for disseminating the full range of research outputs, and recording them on their ORCID Profile allowing them to keep a high-impact record²⁶.

Seek local support from: your librarians; RDM experts (e.g. [Digital Curation Center](#) online training and [DMPOnline](#) tool); [Learn-RDM](#) community; [Data Carpentry](#) community, [Software Carpentry](#) community and the [Sustainable Software Institute](#) trainings; [Data Science Training 4 Librarians](#)²⁷ curriculum and community.

Star 3: Open Peer Review

In addition to the above, train incentivize and recognize peer-review skills and effort²⁸. Include *Open Peer-Review* and *Research Code of Conduct* training to re-inforce high ethical standards in existing “how to peer-review publications” classes, and introduce researchers to recent controversies on the re-hauling the peer-review system.

Rationale: the pillar of high-quality reproducible research is independent validation and critique through peer-review that is learned on the job²⁹, but your graduates understands in-depth the pros and cons of Open Peer-Review³⁰, and how it can be used effectively to teach others³¹ to reach the same level of research transparency for the purpose of impact as well as research integrity. Your graduates know how to keep a public record of their peer-review activity (e.g. [Publons.com - ORCID](#)³² service now online) in anticipation of formal recognition of the effort.

Seek local support from:

[FOSTER Community](#), Horizon 2020 OpenUP Project, journals practicing open peer-review (e.g. *FrontiersIN*, *PLOS One*, *Atmospheric Chemistry & Physics*, *PeerJ*, *British Medical Journal* & *F1000Research*)

Star 4: Winning Research Grants

In addition to the above, provide training on use of Open Science to reinforce responsible, reproducible and re-usable research for optimum career and societal impact (in the context of future research evaluation criteria), as part of existing “how to write a grant proposal” classes.

²⁶ Paragraph 110 in Lord Stern’s review of REF (UK), “Research Excellence Framework Review - Publications - GOV.UK.” July 2016 <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/research-excellence-framework-review>

²⁷ Erdmann, C., 2014. Teaching Librarians to Be Data Scientists, <https://zenodo.org/record/11217#.U-SxTWPzmiU>

²⁸ Nuffield Council on Bioethics. “The Culture of Scientific Research.” Nuffield Bioethics, December 2014. <http://nuffieldbioethics.org/project/research-culture/>

²⁹ The Culture of Scientific Research in the UK, Nuffield Council on Bioethics, Dec 2014. <http://nuffieldbioethics.org/project/research-culture/>

³⁰ What is open peer review? <http://blog.f1000research.com/2014/05/21/what-is-open-peer-review/>

³¹ Aleksic J, et al. 2015. An Open Science Peer Review Oath. *F1000Research* 2015, doi: [10.12688/f1000research.5686.2](https://doi.org/10.12688/f1000research.5686.2)

³² <https://members.orcid.org/api/peer-review-getting-started#who>

For relevant disciplines, train on the synergies and conflicts of Open Science and Open Innovation³³, so that graduate can optimize the use of Open Science tools to effectively transfer new research along the lab-2-market spectrum in full respect of Intellectual Property Right & Privacy issues, while competitively funding³⁴ their research career.

Rationale: your graduates understand the relevance of their research output outside of academia, and your school fosters a counter culture of “science is for scientists” attitude. Research practices training directly supports funders Open Innovation agenda³⁵ and return on investment for funder, institution and society as a whole.

Seek local support from: your National Contact Points (NCPs); FP7 [RRI-Tools Portal & Resources](#); FP7 [FOSTER Portal](#) & [Community Support](#); “[Open Innovation, Open Science, Open to the World](#)” EC Booklet.

Star 5: Engage Society for Impact

In addition to the above, training on *strategic science communication skills, translation of research* in the context of societal challenges and controversies, for the purpose of uptake of open and accessible research into policy, commercial exploitation and for the purposes of engaging citizen scientists in the research process³⁶.

For relevant disciplines, structured training on text/data mining (TDM) skills for navigating the knowledge landscape in an increasingly trans-disciplinary research environment, data visualization, data journalism and successful strategies for capitalizing on citizen science to enhance the research process and engage society in the process.

Rationale: your graduates have the skills to translate complex research into the language of a defined non-academic target group, and engage them in the research process. The skillset allows them to formulate research question with greater clarity³⁷, gaining a competitive edge at grant proposal formulation, as well as developing an alternative career path.

Seek local support from: your local Science Communication experts, or

Online Training & Community Support:

[Compass Online](#), Science Communication training and community
[FastTrackImpact Blog and online training](#) by Professor Mark Reed (author of [Research Impact Handbook](#))

³³ Chesborough, H., 2015. From Open Science to Open Innovation, Report by ScienceBusiness
<http://www.sciencebusiness.net/OurReports/ReportDetail.aspx?ReportId=74>

³⁴ Grigorov et al., 2015. Winning Horizon 2020 with Open Science. Zenodo. [10.5281/zenodo.12247](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12247)

³⁵ Open Innovation, Open Science, Open to the World - a Vision for Europe, European Commission & DG Research & Innovation, <http://bookshop.europa.eu/en/open-innovation-open-science-open-to-the-world-pbKI0416263>

³⁶ Recommendation 7 of Lord Stern REF review, “Research Excellence Framework Review - Publications - GOV.UK.” July 2016. <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/research-excellence-framework-review>.

³⁷ COSEE’s Influence on Scientists’ Professional Practices: Findings from the COSEE Scientist Study, Sept 2012
http://www.cosee.net/files/coseenet/2012_NSF_Sci_Study_Exec_Summary.pdf

[Broader Impact Wizzard](#) (developed by NSF for the Ocean Research community, but with many generic approaches and references to studies and strategies on reaching a broad range of stakeholders)

Books:

[Escape from the Ivory Tower](#) written by COMPASS' Nancy Baron;

[Research Impact Handbook](#) written by Professor Mark Reed ([reviews by Steven Hill, Head of Research Policy at HEFCE](#), UK)

European Commission Resources:

[Communicating your Horizon 2020 project](#)

[Communicating EU research and innovation](#) - Guidance for project participants

Appendix: List of Graduate Schools that attended FOSTER Events under the task:

Open Science: Engaging Finland's Doctoral Schools

20 October 2014

Ministry of Education and Culture, Ivo Grigorov (FOSTER)

Biomedicum Helsinki Haartmaninkatu 8

WHO ATTENDED?

Ilkka Reenilä, DPDR, DPCVM / DSHealth / Univ. Helsinki;
Nina Blom, Univ. of Helsinki;
Gretchen Repasky, FIMM, DSHealth, DPBM, FINDOS;
Keijo Hämäläinen, Univ. of Helsinki;
Katri Vehviläinen-Julkunen, Univ. of Eastern Finland;
Riikka Pellinen, Univ. of Eastern Finland;
Maija Urponen, Univ. of Helsinki;
Sievi Eeva, Univ. of Helsinki;
Maria Ljung, Åbo Akademi University;
Anneli Ahvenniemi, Aalto University;
Tapio Lokki, Aalto University / SCI;
Eeva Valve, University of Turku;
Tua Hindersson-Söderholm, Svenska handelshögskolan;
Jutta Kajander, Univ. of Helsinki;
Riikka Palonkorpi, Helsingin yliopisto;
Hannes Lohi, Univ. of Helsinki;
Antti Mäkitie, Univ. of Helsinki Central Hospital;
Mathias Björklund Hanken, Svenska handelshögskolan;
Maija Tiippana-Usvasalo, Farmasian tiedekunta;
Tuula Oksanen, University of Jyväskylä;
Karen Sims-Huopaniemi, Univ. of Helsinki;
Fredrik Karlsson, Åbo Akademi;
Karin Hemmann, Univ. of Helsinki;
kaisa Korhonen-Kurki, Univ. of Helsinki;
Olli-Pekka Kaurahalme, Turun Yliopisto;
+ anonymous attendees

FOSTER-UNESCO Open Science for Doctoral Schools

23-24 April 2015

Bhanu Neupane (UNESCO), Joy Davidson (DCC), Nancy Pontika (OU) Ivo Grigorov (FOSTER)

1 rue Miollis, 75015 Paris, France

WHO ATTENDED?

Bhanu Neupane (speaker), UNESCO
Silvia Luber (speaker), European Commission
Nancy Pontika (speaker), Open University (UK)
Sami Niinimäki (speaker), Ministry of Education & Culture (FI)
Jean-Francois Gibrat (speaker), French Institute of Bioinformatics (FR)
Marie-Veronique Leroi (speaker), Ministry of Culture & Communication (FR)
Joy Davidson (speaker), Digital Curation Center (UK)
Ivo Grigorov (speaker), Technical University of Denmark (DK)

Participants, Graduate Schools representatives:

Gretchen Repasky, Health Sciences, Un. Helsinki (FI)
Elise Pinta, Doctoral School, University of Turku (FI)
Virpi Juppo, Doctoral School, University of Vaasa (FI)
Nina Bergmann, Integrated School of Ocean Sciences, GEOMAR (DE)
Claudia Delgado, IODE Training Coordinator, UNESCO
Heli Väättäjä, UBINET Doctoral Training Network, UBINET
Matti Nikkola, Developmental Biology for Regenerative Medicine Research School, Karolinska Institute (SE)
Søren Wandahl, Engineering Graduate School of Science & Technology, Aarhus Un. (DK)
Tim Deprez, MARES Doctoral School (www.mares-eu.org) (BE)
Fred Jean, Ecole Doctorale des Sciences de la Mer, Un. West Brittany (FR)
Rayna Stamboliyska, Open Access Advocate
Anita Berglund, Doctoral Programme in Epidemiology, Karolinska Institute (SE)
Vicky Schneider, Norwich Bioscience DTP, (UK)
Malvika Sharan, Graduate School of Life Sciences, Un. Würzburg (AU)
Anneliese Depoux, Centre Virchow-Villermé (USPC), (FR)
Pierre-Carl Langlais, PhD Student (FR)

CONTACTS & SUPPORT:

OpenAIRE HelpDesk:
<https://www.openaire.eu/support/helpdesk>

FOSTER Community:
www.fosteropenscience.eu
[@fosterscience](https://twitter.com/fosterscience)

The Open Science community can also be consulted online at

 [FOSTER Project](#)
 [@fosterscience](https://twitter.com/fosterscience)

Last but not least:

Your research library & Knowledge Managers.

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www.fosteropenscience.eu

doi: 10.5281/zenodo.59185

